

Removal of heavy metals from sugar mill effluent using low cost adsorbent (fly ash)

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Manuscript received 18 July 2005, revised 20 October 2005, accepted 23 May 2006

Abstract : The present study aims at conserving the valuable ground water resource from industrial activity at the root level. Removal of the heavy metals such as Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni from sugar mill effluent using low cost adsorbent, activated fly ash, has been studied. The results show that Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni are removed by about 62, 59, 61 and 57% respectively. Based on this technique the ground water resource can be protected from sugar mill effluent contamination.

Keywords : Heavy metals, adsorption, fly ash.

The heavy metals play a vital role in the normal functioning of human body. Yet, imbalance of any of the heavy metals will disturb the above function. The widespread use of heavy metals in various industries adds to the problem of accidental contamination of natural ecosystem due to poor disposal methods. Normally, effluents discharged from sugar mills constitute number of chemical pollutants including heavy metals. When these effluents are discharged into the environment, they disrupt the ecological cycle of living organisms. The multi-stage production in industries require high amount of organic and inorganic substances and waste water from these is likely to contain the same. This waste water by intrusion pollute the ground water¹. The object of the present study is to conserve this valuable resource from further deterioration, by performing treatment at the preliminary level. Hence an attempt has been made to reduce the heavy metals such as Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni from sugar mill effluent based on the adsorption principle.

Materials and methods :

In the present study, sugar mill effluent was collected from Pettavaithalai area. The heavy metals such as Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni were analysed at different time intervals based on adsorption principle. The low cost adsorbent fly ash was used after acid digestion and thermal activation at 120 °C for 5 h. The chemical composition of fly ash collected from Neyveli is as follows : pH – 9.5, EC (µs/cm) – 1.0, Ca – 1500 mg, Mg – 290 mg, Na – 85 mg, Fe – 40 mg, Zn – 10 mg,

Cu – 2.5 mg, Mn – 20 mg, Ni – 1 mg and B – 2 mg per kg of fly ash. Sample collection and estimations were performed as per the standard methods of Manivasagam² and APHA³.

About 500 ml of the effluent sample was taken in a beaker. 1.0 g of activated fly ash was added to it and it was magnetically stirred. 20 ml of the sample was withdrawn for every 30 min duration and filtered. The concentration of heavy metals such as Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni were estimated from the filtrates. At the end of 3 h, stirring was stopped and the experiment was terminated. The percentage reduction of Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni for different contact time was noted. The experiment was repeated six times for standardizing the procedure and the mean values were tabulated.

Table 1. Percentage reduction of copper, manganese, zinc and nickel with respect to contact time (average of six)

Time (min)	Percentage reduction			
	Cu	Mn	Zn	Ni
30	37	37	37	37
60	45	46	47	44
90	54	52	55	48
120	59	57	59	53
150	62	59	61	57
180	62	59	61	57

Note

Results and discussion

The estimated values of Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni for sugar mill effluent were given in Table 1. The mean results showed that the percentage reduction of heavy metals (Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni) increased with time⁴. It was found that the rate of removal was rapid at the initial stage and became slow and steady with increase in contact time. This might be due to the adequate availability of active sites at the initial period, which brings about adsorption⁵. After 3 h with increase in time there is no change in concentration which shows that a state of equilibrium has attained after a contact time of 3 h⁶.

The treatment revealed that the low cost adsorbent fly ash may be used for removing 62% of Cu, 59% of Mn, 61% of Zn and 57% of Ni from the sugar mill effluent effectively. The same technique can also be extended to the

ground water source and in this way, it can be protected from sugar mill effluent contamination.

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